

A conjecture concerning a formula for prime numbers.

Conjecture. Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \neq n$. There is, then, a formula that can determine exactly how many prime numbers there are between m and n .

Note: In the 19th century, the well-known prime number theorem was proved. This theorem states that between one and any number x , there exist approximately $x/\ln x$ prime numbers, where $\ln x$ is the natural logarithm of x . The problem with this theorem is obvious: the estimate of the number of prime numbers it provides is imprecise and approximate.